

Design, Development and Application of Robotic Arm in the Field of Archaeological Excavations

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Abstract

This paper focuses on the application of the electromechanical design concept of a lead screw actuated, robotic arm gripper in the field of Archaeology. Robotic applications are known to be catering to many industries from a range of tasks namely pick & place, material handling, as fixtures, tool & instrument holders etc. In this application specific robots are equipped with end effectors customized with design, appropriate for the application. In this paper, the details are presented for the design of an end effector also known as the robotic arms which works on a lead screw linear mechanism actuated by a dc motor. The mechanical construction for this unique robotic arm gripper mechanism is observed to be robust and can be used as an end effector to a suitable robotic application. There are numerous archaeological fields on earth, in which the majority of the civilizations, the ancient physical remnants have been buried with time. Therefore, reaching all points of any archaeological site becomes quite difficult. Sometimes areas are not accessible in this condition and it becomes dangerous for people to reach without any instruments at all. Thus some device is needed to address the problem that will help in discovering the unknown and unreachable areas. The robotic arm will serve the purpose of such archaeological endeavours.

Key Words: Robotic Arm, Robotic Grippers, Lead Screw, Archaeological excavation

Introduction

Due to increasing demand in archeological research, innovation in this area is expanding rapidly. As there are many archaeological research areas present on earth, in which most of the civilizations, antiquities, old physical remains have got buried under the earth and water levels, with the passing of time. So, it becomes very challenging to reach to every point of any archeological site. In this condition sometime places are not reachable and it becomes risky for the archaeologists to reach there without any tools. To resolve the problem some instrument is required which can reach to those spots or provide a glimpse to know more about those places. The present study aims at introducing a machine which can solve those problems to give an extra edge in archeological research. This machine has potential of going deep down under water surface and also capable of going deep under the surface to capture the evidences of ancient civilizations, and to collect samples, specimens or any other object from the site.

Figure 1 CAD assembly model Robotic Arm Gripper

Figure 1 gives an initial overview of this Robotic arm gripper which will be used in archeological survey and excavations (Krishnaraju, et.al. 2015).

It is having a movable arm with gripping jaw which could be sent to the underground via bore-well or could be sent to the deep water directly. It consists of a set of cameras which can constantly monitor the surrounding area and take pictures or videos which might reveal what is in there underwater or underground. It is completely battery operated and rechargeable, which

allows this machine to be taken anywhere for use without any hesitation in power source (Aparisii Escriva, 2016).

Objective of the Study

In archaeology, excavation is the exposure, processing and recording of archaeological remains. An excavation site or "dig" is the area being studied. These locations range from one to several areas at a time during an excavation and can be conducted over a few weeks to several years.

Before excavating, the presence or absence of archaeological remains can often be suggested by, non-intrusive remote sensing, such as ground-penetrating radar and explorations of the site. Basic information about the development of the site may be drawn from this work, but to understand finer details of a site, excavation via auguring can be used & for understanding more finer details the machine which has been developed will investigate in deep down through bore-well before the actual excavation.

This machine is an automatic specimen collecting & investigating machine which can telecast live video in the panel & images from the bore-well underground or it could be sent to the deep water directly as it is water proof. As this machine has a robotic arm with Robotic Gripper Mechanism, it is capable of collecting the soil sample or antiques from underground.

Area of Study

In this particular paper the different applications of robotic arm in the archeological operation have been discussed.

Basically, this machine can investigate the area before the excavation in archeological operation. Its robotic arm goes down the bore-well for collecting soil sample & giving a clear view under the ground of the excavation site. By this machine a better idea about the time period of the layers of earth or soil can be obtained as well as the data related to the antiques.

So the basic area of study is the robo-gripper mechanism with some modification for better investigation & to understand the finer details in deep down.

Structural Component of Robotic Arm

The robotic arm gripper is an assembly of several parts as follows: -

1. 4 jaws- dimensions: (120-118mm in overall length
30/20/10mm base
Two 4mm diameter hole)
2. 20 plane metallic strips- dimensions: (40/10mm with 4mm diameter hole at each end)
3. 4 two planner metallic strips-dimensions: (40/20mm)
4. 1 cubic metallic block with internal threading (40/30mm
20mm hole
6mm pitch)
5. 1 lead screw of 200mm in length/ 20mm in cross section.

6. 2 DC motors of 12v,24v.236 rpm
7. 1 conveyor pulley with anti-rust metallic rope
8. 5 waterproof cameras: 12 MP

Motors are used to power the pulley and also to rotate the lead screw. The rotation of the pulley helps the robotic arm to reciprocate up and down. The 2nd motor rotates the lead screw. Then the lead screw triggers the cubic block which is connected with it by internal threading. This makes the metallic strips to reciprocate and ultimately the force is transmitted to the jaws and then the desired output is availed (Eitel, 2010).

Methodology

This research paper will also facilitate Heritage management and helps to preserve the antiquities during the excavation processes. The research was started keeping in view lowering the expense and costing while doing excavation or digging at any archeological site. The key aim of this paper is to promote the use of technology and innovation in any archeological survey or excavation.

Methodology involves the following the steps of Fig 2 with collecting theoretical, conceptual and technical information about the excavation processes and then analyzed the difficulties faced in any excavation process with a step-by-step flow chart.

Figure 2 Methodology

Different suitability parameters and other relevant data required to develop the robotic arm are collected from an archeological site during survey and excavation process. These are considered from the point of the difficulties faced during excavation process, identifying the soil layers or testing of soil. As we know that, the technology and technological resources in archeological processes is very limited, so one has to follow the conventional process of site surveying or excavation. While doing the surveys and research on the problems of archeological operations like excavation processes and water body surveys, the main issues are raised when the sub-soil water prevents to go further below or the challenges faced in underwater excavation. Water bodies refer to river, pond, lakes, sea or any watery area where the presence of antiquities is suspected.

The main difficulty in any water body is, searching for any antiquities, artifacts and other physical remain beneath the water surface for a long time. According to conventional procedure for surveying under the water surface, divers are sent for collecting the information from there. Now from here, a problem arises that the diver needs many gadgets and equipment and also most importantly the oxygen cylinder to dive under the water. Because of this oxygen limitation divers are not capable to explore the region for long time and along with this it can be also observed that general divers do not possess much knowledge in archeological aspects.

Figure 3 Divers exploring the city of Dwarka

The Archeological Survey of India (ASI) has its eye on underwater exploration since the mid of - 1970s. Figure 3 shows the exploration of man-made structures off the coast of Dwarka by scuba divers, where a handful of explorers have always borne a disproportionate workload. In 1990, S.R. Rao, named the father of marine archaeology in India, who supervised the Dwarka dives, observed that ‘five diving archeologists is too small a number for a country of the size of India. (Sudarshan Aditya, THE HINDU, 2017)

So, due to lack of resources and technology in marine archeology it gets difficult to explore any water body for archeological purpose. Due to this lack of technology and resources in India excavating or surveying any place on land for archeological purpose also has certain limitations. At the time of excavation in any archeological site, after digging several layers of earth the groundwater surfaces and excavation gets restricted and from there it gets difficult to go beyond the ground water. Thus, by means of conventional process only up to a certain level of earth surface can be explored or excavated.

Figure 4 Soil Layers

Figure 5 Ground Water and Water table

From Figure 4 and Figure 5 it is clearly understandable that after digging several layers of earth in the form of well, groundwater comes in the way and after the level of groundwater a rocky layer occurs.

Thus, considering all facts and figures, the design of the Robotic arm has been modified in such a way that it can be sent directly to the remote area under the earth surface where human beings cannot reach easily for further archaeological research work. The Robotic arm is supported by a solid structure through a metallic chain and a conveyor pulley. This metallic structure acts as a base from earth surface, which consists of control panel for the operator to operate arm in remote area while standing above the earth surface. In addition to these, it is also equipped with five waterproof cameras, an underwater LED light and a direction mapping module. Mechanisms of each equipped gadgets in Robotic arm are described below.

Camera

There are five cameras mounted on the 'Robotic Arm' which will specifically capture the images and videos of remote area under water surface and each camera will be able to capture the images and scenes in different angle.

Figure 6 Camera 1 mounted in the middle of jaw

Figure 7 4 Cameras mounted on motor casing

In Figure 6 and Figure 7 each camera is shown where it is mounted on motor casing, which will monitor the surroundings in different direction.

These cameras could be operated by operator according to their use while staying on the earth surface. These are totally waterproof and can work in any surroundings. Main task of the cameras is to monitor the scenes when the robotic gripper will be in remote area to grab the objects. Cameras are powered by 5V power supply and operated using Wi-Fi technology with a range of (700-800) m from earth surface.

Lights

In Figure 6, four pairs of waterproof LED lights are mounted below the geared motor casing. The CAD model design of LED lights is done on CAD software. These lights are mounted on motor casing for better image capturing of surroundings of robotic gripper jaw. This light will illuminate the surrounding and operator will get better quality of images when Robotic Arm will be in working mode in remote area.

Scientific analysis

As this “Robotic Arm” has several parts and each part works on different theories and principle so we will see the working analysis of each part.

Mechanical Function of Robotic Arm Gripper

The design of robotic arm gripper mechanism is progressed to a high level. This involves construction of complex mechanical system as demanded by level of dexterity required by the end application. This paper describes a simple construction of a robotic arm gripper which will grip antiquities and ancient remains under water surface efficiently. CAD assembly model of robotic arm gripper is attached for better understanding of mechanism.

Figure 8 CAD model of Robotic Gripper

An overview of mechanical design of the robotic arm gripper is shown in the CAD assembly model picture in Figure 8. The gripper plate is designed to hold the object against the jaw with force exerted by the metallic strip moving on the lead screw. The lead screw is driven by a geared motor coupled with flexible coupling. The lead screw rotates in the bearing housed in the fixture. There is a guide metallic cube having internal threads attached with lead screw moves linearly. The condition for effective grip for the jaw grippers during normal object pick & movement is mathematically given by,

$$\text{Gripping force, } F(\text{grip}) > (m \times g / \mu(\text{grip})) \times \text{F.O.S} \times N$$

Where,

m = weight of the object being gripped, kg

$\mu(\text{grip})$ = coefficient of friction between the object and gripping surface

F.O.S = factor of safety recommended based on motion

g = acceleration due to gravity, m/s^2

Mathematical formulations of the gripping are made in earlier studies for the intended compliance and dexterity of the end effector. However, the scope and simplicity of the robotic jaw gripper allows us to make use of straight forward engineering calculations. Objects of various shapes are often handled by modular robotic grippers. Robotic jaw works on Screw principle. Screw principle is simple mechanism that converts rotational motion to linear motion and a torque (Rotational force) to linear force. (Krishnamoorthy, 2019).

Mechanical function of conveyor pulley

Conveyor pulley is one of the essential parts of this machine (robotic arm) in which metallic ropes are wraps around it. One end of this metallic rope is coupled with pulley and on another end “Robotic Jaw” is connected. Rotation of conveyor pulley in its fixed horizontal axis help to fold and unfold the metallic rope and also help to calculate the distance travelled by Robotic arm under the water surface. The metallic ropes are anti-rust galvanized coated made of stainless steel. Conveyor pulley is operated using 24V power supply. When the motor will be powered up it will start to rotate and along with it, and the coupled conveyor pulley will also start to rotate in its fixed axis. Both this motor and conveyor pulley are mounted on a metallic rigid structure which has four legs to support these parts on it.

Figure 9 CAD model of Conveyor pulley and metallic rope

Figure 9 shows the mechanical design of conveyor pulley and metallic rope as CAD assembly picture. This design is made for better understanding of pulley and rope mechanism in robotic arm operation. Conveyor pulley is one of the essential parts of this machine (robotic arm) in which metallic ropes are wrapped around it. One end of this metallic rope is coupled with pulley and on another end “Robotic Jaw” is connected. Rotation of conveyor pulley in its fixed horizontal axis help to fold and unfold the metallic rope and also help to calculate the distance travelled by Robotic arm under the water surface. The metallic ropes are anti-rust galvanized coated made of stainless steel.

Distance or length of depth travelled by arm is computed as:

$$d = 2\pi R \times \text{no. of rotation of conveyor pulley}$$

Where, d = Travelled distance
 r = Radius of conveyor pulley.

Component Selection

Based on theoretical calculation and also keeping in mind the sourcing & cost criteria, components are selected for this prototype CAD model assembly. The DC motor is suitable for the voltage range of 12V, 24V and maximum output torque of 20N-cm. The gear box can be customized with different revolutions and torque. To meet the application requirements, with output torque, high performance, high precision, high starting torque, low speed, easy to dissemble.

<p>Motor:</p> <p>Description DC 12V,24V 236rpm high torque, low rpm geared motor</p> <p>Specification:</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Motor Type</td> <td>DC geared motor</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Operating voltage(VDC)</td> <td>12, 24</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Rated current(A)</td> <td>0.8 to 1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Rated Speed(RPM)</td> <td>236</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Operating Temperature(°C)</td> <td>-40 to 100</td> </tr> </table> <p>12MP WATERPROOF CAMERA</p>	Effective still resolution	12MP	Optical sensor resolution	12MP	Operating voltage	5V	Operating Temperature	-10°C to 80°C	Aspect ratio	16:9											
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Camera is selected for a minimum weight of 126gm, which have features like improved HDR and super photo with 4k 60 wide and 1080P 240 wide and having connected feature of wifi+Bluetooth, GPS enabled so that it can be used in specific application when it is operated. It is waterproof and can work in any surroundings. This camera is having special feature of more durable and not easy to wear. Special Application is video recording under water surface for a long time.

Mechatronics System Concept

The mechatronic approach gives a blend of sensing, actuation and control to the mechanical design. The level of intelligence needed by the system is limited by the degree of sophistication required and cost of development for the intended application. Figure 10 gives an overview of the mechatronic concept for the Robotic Arm Gripper Design.

Along with the objective to design & develop a robust mechanical construction for the Robotic Arm gripper, the performance of the conveyor pulley, motors and gripper jaw by means of on/off signal given to the motor actuator has to be understood. As mentioned earlier the lead screw actuator is powered by the 12V or 24V dc motor. Also shown in earlier figures, a dc motor driver is employed which is based on the Arduino and motor driver integrated chip, is capable of bidirectional control of dc and stepper motors.

Figure 10 Mechatronic system concept for Robotic Arm Gripper

All the components and parts of this Robotic Arm Gripper are controlled by Arduino and Motor shield which take input signal from operator via controller and gives the output voltage to the actuators. The controller part of the system is not investigated in the system prototype development. This could be an embedded controller which should take the feedback signal from the Force Sensing Resistor (F.S.R) for further processing and control. In Figure 11a CAD model of Arduino is shown for better understanding.

Figure 11 CAD model of Arduino Circuit Board

System Development & Testing Overview

Engineering manufacturing drawings are developed for metal fabrication process through which the strippers & gripper plates are developed. Again, the manufacturing drawings are created with the help of the CAD tool. 'Design for manufacturing' principle is employed in designing these metal parts wherein standard bend features, standard uniform hole sizes and addition of slots for weight reduction are considered in the design. Finger-like features are added to the parts to give them look typical to a hand shaped robotic end effector.

Figure 12 Testing overview of the system

The designing and assembly of the Robotic Arm Gripper is done in CAD software. An operational and functional overview of the system is shown in figure 12 where the robotic arm is shown to operate in bore well to collect the specimen from deep down the earth surface. The robotic arm will go down with the help of rotating of conveyor pulley and unfolding of metallic rope and then after going down, jaw will start its mechanism to grab the specimen below. The grabbing mechanism will process after lead screw movement. An operating voltage of 12V is required in geared motor to rotate the lead screw. After the grabbing of specimen, the pulley motor rotates in reverse direction to fold the metallic rope so that the robotic arm could climb up to earth surface while holding the specimen. Later the specimen will be collected very carefully from the robotic jaw for archeological research purpose.

Conclusion

The operating and performance of the Robotic Arm Gripper yields favorable results in gathering specimens, soil samples, artifacts, or any ancient materials from deep beneath the earth's surface and under the water's surface for archaeological study. The robustness of the mechanical design involving the conveyor pulley, anti-rust metallic chain, metallic strips & gripper plates and its

application are well understood. Performance of the motor actuated lead screw results on gripping action, since the lead screw is known have negligible backlash. Functional overview of the Robotic Arm gripper by gripping the objects gives satisfactory results on the gripping performance. Using the PLC (programmable logic controller i.e. Arduino) to control the machine is a matter of further research from a control engineering standpoint. The mechanical design is made keeping in view of attaching this standalone end effector to a robotic arm. This could be a standard pick & place robotic application in any Archeological excavation and also in any other industry.

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